

Federating cross-domain BIM-based knowledge graph

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ABSTRACT

Despite decades of the digitization of the construction industry, interoperability challenges prevail. One of which is the lack of sufficient integration between domain-specific BIM models. Therefore, the paper proposes a novel methodology for federating cross-domain BIM-based knowledge graphs. The approach leverages the integration of multiple models into a single knowledge graph, aiming to bridge the existing gaps in data exchange and enhance the semantic richness of building information models. Through a detailed exploration of existing data exchange mechanisms, popular ontologies, and schema limitations, this research addresses the interoperability dilemma. A practical demonstration, encapsulated in the “LBD-Online-Merge” demo application, validates the methodology’s efficacy in real-world scenarios, illustrating its potential to revolutionize building operations management and data preparation for the operational phase of a building’s lifecycle. This study significantly contributes to the academic and practical discourse by providing a robust framework for achieving a more integrated, intelligent building information management ecosystem, setting a new benchmark for future research and applications in constructing semantically rich digital twins of the built environment.

1. Introduction

The construction industry underwent significant transformation with the advent of technologies like computer-aided design (CAD) and Building Information Modelling (BIM) [1]. BIM, originally conceptualised by Eastman, revolutionised the industry by integrating virtual building models with comprehensive databases, advanced visualisation, and quantitative analysis, addressing the growing complexity of construction projects [2,3]. The formation of the International Alliance for Interoperability (IAI), now known as buildingSMART, in 1994 and the subsequent release of the Industry Foundation Classes (IFC) in 1997 marked major milestones in promoting industry interoperability, standardisation, and enhanced productivity. IFC gained significance, underpinned by its fundamental role in the ISO 19650 standard series. These requirements guide the BIM methodology across various phases, from initial design to the final stages of a building’s lifecycle. IFC’s role as a key openBIM standard is crucial for

interdisciplinary coordination and data exchange, facilitating the integration of various stakeholders [4]. Within the Architecture, Engineering, Construction and Operation (AECO) sector, data structured according to the IFC schema is increasingly recognised for enhancing the efficiency and effectiveness of building operation phases [1,5,6].

One of the escalating technological advancements in the operation phase is the concept proposed by Michael Grieves. The Digital Twin (DTw) concept emerges, offering a promising pathway for reducing environmental impact [7]. The bidirectional link between physical and virtual instances of a construction object provides multiple applications capable of controlling, managing, and detecting anomalies during the operation phase of the lifecycle [5,8,9]. Studies agreed that applying such a sophisticated concept requires a machine and human-interpretable data structure [5]. The key initiative being broadly adopted is the knowledge graph approach, particularly semantic web technologies. It provides a human and machine-interpretable technology capable of integrating diverse sources of information. One of the

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most feasible data acquisition approaches is converting the BIM model to a compatible Resource Description Framework (RDF) [5,10,11].

Various research initiatives have proposed converting BIM models into RDF-compatible data formats to expand integration options and address interoperability issues [12–14]. While this conversion offers the advantage of a more accessible and flexible data structure, it cannot inherently uncover new relational insights at the intersections of domain-specific BIM models. This limitation leads to information redundancy without explicitly linking instances representing the same physical entity. Consequently, this results in a notable research gap that hampers semantic reasoning and impacts interoperability. Specifically, this gap impedes the comprehensive understanding of connections and dependencies among various building components, which is crucial for achieving a holistic view of building information models. This lack of clarity and the resulting fragmentation significantly challenge the industry's move towards integrated and semantically rich digital twins, underscoring the urgency and significance of addressing these interoperability barriers [12,13].

This study focuses on closing the gap between converting stand-alone BIM models into RDF formats and introduces the concept of a federating cross-domain BIM-based knowledge graph. The research is structured around three core questions:

How to efficiently create a Federated Knowledge Graph based on domain-specific BIM Models? (RQ1)

How to integrate domain-specific models into a Federated Knowledge Graph? (RQ2)

What are the advantages of employing a BIM-based Federated Knowledge Graph? (RQ3)

The paper aims to address a technical gap in BIM-to-RDF conversion and propose an approach for creating a knowledge graph that can potentially revolutionise cross-domain interactions in construction and architectural design. Currently, the expression of the BIM model in RDF form is limited to the scope of a single file. Therefore, this paper aims to close this gap by presenting a novel concept integrating multiple models and stakeholders and closing the gap caused by the stand-alone conversion process.

To understand the foundations of this issue, the paper begins with an Introduction in Section 1, laying the groundwork for the study and introducing the research problem. Section 2 provides a background picture, offering an overview of relevant literature to set the context for the research. Section 3 outlines the materials and methods used. Section 4 introduces the developed application used to test the proposed methodology. Section 5 demonstrates the use of the methodology, including processing time and the number of newly discovered connections. The Discussion in Section 6 is divided into two parts. The first focuses on demonstrating the proposed framework's usage through multiple SPARQL queries and discusses its application. The second part delves into the limitations and key features of the concept, offering a critical analysis. Finally, the last section concludes and summarises the key findings and implications of the study.

2. Literature review

The section navigates the complex interoperability landscape in the construction industry, examining the underlying challenges that hamper data exchange and collaboration among stakeholders. It highlights the historical reliance on technological advancements as a primary solution, pointing to the critical realization that such measures alone are insufficient without standardized processes and data management practices. The review then transitions to exploring the role of BIM in facilitating improved interoperability, underscoring its significance in promoting efficient collaboration and standardization across the industry's fragmented nature. Further, it delves into the specifics of BIM data workflow, detailing how it streamlines project management and addresses

interoperability challenges through a structured data environment. It also covers the limitations of the IFC schema in supporting comprehensive data integration and their potential as a data input for semantic web technologies to enhance interoperability. The final part of the discussion focuses on how linked data is being leveraged to push the boundaries of interoperability in construction, aiming for a more interconnected and effective approach to project data management.

2.1. Interoperability

In addressing the interoperability challenges within the construction industry, it is crucial to recognise its underlying factors [14]. The AECO is known for complex processes, stakeholder diversity, and intricate geometrical aspects contributing to significant interoperability problems [15,16]. Historically, these issues were primarily attributed to data fragmentation and a lack of standardised data exchange formats [14]. In response, there was a heavy emphasis on developing more sophisticated tools, machinery automation, and software efficiency. However, a pivotal shift in understanding emerged in the early 2000s when the industry realised that the solution to these challenges does not solely lie in the continual development of advanced tools [14]. Instead, there was a need to return to the basics: establishing firm standards and well-structured process flows.

This shift is particularly relevant in light of the industry's fragmented nature, with most of the workforce employed in small companies. These small entities often lack the resources to adopt and effectively utilise advanced processes, exacerbating interoperability issues. The diverse and decentralised character of the industry necessitates a more unified approach to data management and process standardisation [15,16]. In this context, BIM methodology becomes even more crucial, offering a platform for collaboration and data sharing across different stages of an object lifecycle. However, its effectiveness relies heavily on standardised and legally established processes [10].

Moreover, as technology advances, the industry faces the challenge of ensuring that new tools and processes are accessible and adaptable for all stakeholders, regardless of their size and resources. This includes fostering an environment where data can be easily shared and understood across various software systems, bridging the gap caused by heterogeneous IT adoption [5,10]. Therefore, while technological advancements remain important, they must be complemented by efforts to standardise processes and promote a culture of collaboration and open communication. It is crucial to clarify that technology and standardization are essential elements but serve different roles. Technology refers to the innovative tools and systems developed to improve efficiency, whereas standardization involves establishing uniform procedures and criteria to ensure interoperability, quality, and compatibility across the industry [16]. Therefore, the interoperability challenges should be first addressed by proper standardisation and then supplemented by tools development.

2.2. BIM-based data workflow

The advancement of BIM within a Common Data Environment (CDE) has significantly streamlined the workflow in construction projects, enhancing collaboration among stakeholders and addressing interoperability challenges [1]. A CDE is a digital space that serves as a single source of information for the project, facilitating the management, distribution, and collaboration of documents, models, issue management and other data among all project participants [17]. The application of BIM methodology, as defined by the ISO 19650 methodology, plays a crucial role in this context. The series of ISO 19650 standards provides a framework for managing information, including data exchange, versioning, and information organisation across all construction project phases. Its effectiveness supports processes and ensures a smooth information transition throughout the project's lifecycle due to structuring the CDE into four sections: Work in Progress (WIP), SHARED,

PUBLISHED, and ARCHIVE [18,19].

Each section represents a different stage in the data's lifecycle, from initial development in WIP to final archival. This structure allows for the controlled data progression, starting with individual BIM models in the WIP section. These models then move to the SHARED section for federation, a crucial step for contextual understanding and coordination across different domains or quality checks. Once verified, data is transferred to the PUBLISHED container for legitimate use by project stakeholders. Subsequently, when a new version of a file occurs at any container, the old version is relegated to the ARCHIVE, as depicted in Fig. 1.

Based on the shifting of BIM models from one informational container to another, the federation process occurs. This process is crucial for integrating and coordinating multiple discipline-specific models within a Common Data Environment (CDE), allowing stakeholders to allocate and view modelled elements in the context of the entire project. It enables a holistic approach to project planning and management by bringing together architectural, structural, and MEP models, among others, into a unified representation. This federated model is utilized for various purposes, such as clash detection, where overlapping elements are identified and resolved, and construction planning, facilitating a more efficient project execution [1,5,20]. However, it is important to note that while the federation process enhances the coordination of the project, it does not provide new knowledge or relationships emerging between the models' intersections beyond their visual alignment.

Each model uses levels and spaces to have a spatial structure that enables interpretation within its scope. Therefore, the federation process of multiple files leads to a redundancy in the spatial structure without a clear link between them, restricting the potential of the full collaborative approach. A major contributing factor is the structure and requirements of the IFC schema [1]. Despite widespread adoption, constraints pose a significant challenge in moving towards a richer, more informative collaborative environment, enabling interdomain linkage [22].

2.3. IFC limitations

The efficient alignment of models in three-dimensional space does not provide additional relations and knowledge links beyond the confines of the original files [1,13]. This deficiency is primarily attributed to the rigid schema of IFC, its scope in format definitions, and the

Fig. 1. Dataflow across a common data environment.

redundancy of components that permit multiple expressions of identical information [6,21,22]. Constraints hinder the design stage of construction projects and diminish the utility of information during the hand-over, operation, and maintenance phases, ultimately impacting organisational efficiency and benefits [10,23–25].

The limitation in the range of required information or parameters is a critical aspect. The existing rigid schema of IFC does not allow for an easy extension or inclusion of additional relevant data, creating a bottleneck in data flow and knowledge sharing [6,26]. This rigidity means crucial information, which could enhance the efficiency and accuracy of projects compared to physical assets, cannot be easily linked. Consequently, this limitation severely impedes interoperability by obstructing the seamless exchange and integration of diverse data sets essential in the multidisciplinary AECO sector.

The integration of these factors has notably boosted the AECO community's interest in semantic web technologies. This interest arises from viewing these technologies as a potential solution to the fragmented and diverse nature of the construction industry [5,6]. These technologies offer a flexible, extensible, and dynamic data structure. They enable the integration of a broader spectrum of data and facilitate a more interconnected and intelligent AECO ecosystem behind the horizon of currently established standards [27]. This paradigm shift towards semantic web technologies promises to bridge the existing gaps in interoperability and heralds a new era of efficiency and collaboration in the construction industry [5,21,28].

2.4. Linked data

The challenge of achieving interoperability in the construction industry is only partially addressed by software vendors through limited import and export functionalities. These solutions, while helpful, fall short of being comprehensive [29]. The inception of linked data in AECO dates back to the early 2000s, influenced by the development of the Semantic Web [21,30]. This era signified a transition toward unifying diverse data sources, aiming to improve interoperability and process efficiency in construction [31]. The industry's growing emphasis on BIM has been a key driver in the widespread adoption of linked data, promoting more integrated and intelligent data management throughout various phases of construction projects. Linked data's adaptable and scalable nature facilitates the incorporation of varied information sources like the Internet of Things (IoT), the Digital Twin concept, and Geographic Information Systems (GIS) without being confined to a static data structure [5,10,32].

Contrasting with the more rigid, predefined and inflexible structure of the Industry Foundation Classes (IFC), linked data employs Semantic Web technologies to create connections among different data sources. It uses Uniform Resource Identifiers (URIs) for identification and relies on ontologies to define relationships within the data [29]. The RDF is a key component in this approach, using a triplet format consisting of a subject, predicate, and object to store data in a knowledge base.

To provide both human and machine-interpretable reasoning, semantic web technologies employ ontologies. Gruber et al. [33] describes an ontology as a formalised representation of a commonly understood conceptual framework, meaning that an ontology delineates the various concepts and outlines the interconnections among them, typically in a structured manner. Numerous research studies have delved into the methodology of creating, reviewing and merging ontologies for various purposes [6,10,19,34]. However, this research examines ontologies directly linked to express IFC structure as linked data.

2.4.1. Mapping BIM data to RDF

The foundational aspect of established ontologies is their core, which serves as a robust base for expanding other concepts. Within Semantic Web technologies, this foundational core is the Web Ontology Language (OWL). OWL plays a crucial role in defining and creating Web ontologies, offering extensive tools for formally expressing knowledge. These

tools facilitate the definition of classes, properties, individuals, and their interactions, thus establishing and utilising complex relations and terms for knowledge exchange and integration across varied systems. Beetz et al. [22] suggested representing the IFC schema directly in a Semantic Web format, addressing and innovating in the interoperability challenge by ifcOWL. However, extended use of the ontology highlighted issues like an overwhelming number of classes and relation types, impacting its practicality [23,35]. A new approach was introduced by Rasmussen et al. [36] with the Building Topology Ontology (BOT). This concise, modular ontology represents building structures using a few basic classes and predicates. This trend continued with Kukkonen et al. [37] and Pauen et al. [38] proposing the Flow System Ontology (FSO) and Tubes System Ontology (TSO), respectively. Both are designed to describe the Mechanical, Electrical, and Plumbing (MEP) systems in construction projects, known for their complexity and the level of interdependency.

Beyond component relationships, some knowledge graphs extend their functionality to encompass properties of these components, often termed PROPS. In this framework, when using converters, the property host (component) is determined as a subject. The predicate is formed by appending a parameter name to a namespace URI, with the object being the parameter's value. Additionally, the representation might integrate geometrical data facilitated by the Ontology for Managing Geometry (OMG) [39]. This includes detailed descriptions of dimensions, spatial relationships, and the geometrical shapes of building components. For example, it can elaborate on the exact coordinates of a 3D model's vertices, the angular relationships between structural elements, or the curvature of architectural features, thereby providing a comprehensive and precise visualization of the physical attributes of construction elements within a digital framework.

The potential of BIM models can be further enhanced by incorporating the Ontology for Property Management (OPM) [40]. This approach is specifically designed to manage data during the operational phase of a building's lifecycle. Moreover, ontologies like Brick, Real-EstateCore, SAREF, and others offer a comprehensive framework for describing a building and its intricate service systems [41–43]. The choice of ontology hinges on the desired detail and granularity for component descriptions. New ontologies emerging daily play a crucial role in evolving data management strategies, steering towards enhanced data integration within the construction sector.

The role of ontologies in the realm of information description is notably significant. It is essential to comprehend the process of converting IFC data into a format compatible with RDF. Table 1 illustrates a range of open-source tools, detailing their respective technology stacks, utilised ontologies, programming languages, compatible IFC versions, and the ontologies employed in the final output.

The IFCToRDF converter, developed by Pauwels et al. [44], employs the ifcOWL ontology to reflect the IFC schema closely, demonstrating a high level of detail and complex relationships between elements. In contrast, the IFCToLBD, developed by Oraskari et al. [45], extends the

ifcOWL ontology with additional modular ontologies endorsed by the Linked Building Data (LBD) group, aiming to provide a more versatile representation of building elements. This extension is particularly valuable in addressing the various relationships and dependencies within the construction elements. Lastly, the IFC-LBD tool by Rasmussen et al. [46] adopts a simplified approach using LBD ontologies to reduce the resulting graph structure complexity. This simplicity is intended to facilitate a better understanding of the relationships and dependencies among the components. Moreover, it employs FSO and TSO ontologies, which significantly amend the interpretability of MEP components relations and system dependencies.

2.4.2. Data federation and cross-domain connectivity

The advantage of semantic web technologies lies in their ability to merge, extend, and federate data. This capability has sparked a growing trend in the AECO industry, leading to the development of multiple initiatives [28]. A notable example is the work of Werbrouck et al. [27], who proposed integrating issue management through BIM Collaboration Format (BCF) files with distributed pods of domain information. This approach aligns with the demonstration by O'Donnell et al. [24], suggesting integrating cross-domain knowledge, including real-time data, to enhance building performance and facilitate rapid decision-making. In a similar vein, Curry et al. [10] introduced a framework that intertwines an organisation graph with the IFC model, thereby enhancing the interlink between information silos and energy intelligence.

It is critical to recognise that all these concepts require a high level of interoperability of the data and a focus on the use of IFC models. Due to the data fragmentation, schema limitations and various naming conventions, achieving the required level of interdomain connectivity requires a significant effort and well-established modelling practices. Moreover, the lack of all relationships between models and the redundancy of the spatial structure elements makes the process hard to control and achieve a firm result [12,13]. Therefore, a graph-based representation of knowledge offers a pathway to overcoming these obstacles by enabling linkage between domain-specific models. Supplementing such structure with standards and protocols offered by semantic web technologies elevates this potential by explicitly defining relationships, making the linkage between different elements clear and meaningful [5,10,21]. The primary unresolved challenge lies in establishing a universal framework capable of transforming a set of static BIM models into an interconnected data structure capable of defining interdomain linkage.

3. Materials and methods

The following section details the materials used for testing and proposed methodology validation. It describes developed IFC models and the specification of the converter. The next section proposes a structure of steps to enable the cross-domain federation process of BIM models, describing details and key assumptions of each methodology step.

3.1. Materials

3.1.1. IFC models

The employed case study is an enhanced version of the publicly available "Duplex Apartment" model, tailored to meet modelling requirements [47]. This architectural model illustrates a dual-apartment building, where each apartment spans across four distinct levels: the Foundation Level, Level 0, Level 1, and the Roof. Each apartment is designed with ten rooms, and one additional space covers the whole roof area.

The total usable space of the building is 238.84 m², divided equally between the two apartments. The original architecture model was modified, including creating two ventilation shafts, for MEP design feasibility and the ceiling height modification by lowering it from 2.6 m

Table 1
Reviewed IFC to RDF-compatible format converters.

Name	IFCToRDF	IFCToLBD	IFC-LBD
Latest version	0.4	2.41.0	0.3.8
Latest release date	29.08.2020	06.03.2023	14.06.2023
Reference	[44]	[45]	[46]
Language	Java	Java, Python	TypeScript
IFC version	IFC2x3, IFC4	IFC2x3, IFC4, IFC4x3	IFC2x3, IFC4*
Resulting file format	TTL	TTL	TTL
Supported ontologies	ifcOWL	ifcOWL, BOT, OMG, OPM, PROPS, Product	BOT, FSO, PROPS, Product, TSO

* FSO converter does not support IFC4.

to 2.5 m.

The architectural layout was used to design three additional models, representing heating and cooling, piping and ventilation domains. Each file contains 21 spaces and three levels reflecting the building's structure based on the architectural model and providing stand-alone interpretability. All models were created using Revit 2021 software [48]. For enhanced compatibility and framework usage demonstration, models were exported to the IFC format 2x3. This was done using the Model View Definition (MVD) in its Coordination View 2.0 version. All four IFC models are publicly available, and their visual representation is presented in Fig. 2 [49].

The light blue element at the top of the architectural model represents a space reflecting the roof area. Similar spaces are also present in three other models, but for clarity of the figure, they were hidden to focus on other domain-specific elements. Despite the spatial structure element similarities, each domain-specific file contains multiple elements characteristic of the represented domain. The architectural model presented in Fig. 2 contains key elements defining the building's shape and functional layout: furniture, walls, doors, stairs, windows, foundations, ceilings, rooms, slabs and a roof. On the other hand, the heating and cooling model features a boiler, radiators, pipes, and fittings. It incorporates two primary systems: the hydronic supply and hydronic return. These systems circulate water to the radiators and subsequently return it to the boiler.

The third model represents the piping domain, encompassing various components such as sinks, toilet bowls, water heaters, pipes, pipe transitions, fittings, a water meter, and valves. It includes three distinct systems: domestic hot water, domestic cold water, and wastewater. The domestic cold-water system is connected to sinks, toilet bowls, and water heaters, which also marks the beginning of the domestic hot-water system. Additionally, all toilet bowls and sinks are linked to the wastewater system.

The last file is associated with the ventilation domain. It encompasses elements such as air terminals, ducts, fittings, transitions, two air handling units, and four systems types. The first system functions to supply air from the intake to the air handling unit (AHU), then distributes it to rooms via air terminals. Air is then returned to the AHU through terminals and ducts. Subsequently, the waste air is expelled outdoors through the extract air system.

Despite accurate modelling and attention to detail between MEP

models, software and IFC schema limitations prevent displaying six relationships between elements not housed within a single IFC file. Due to the symmetrical characteristics of the model, each missing relationship listed below occurs on the other side of the building between twin components. Three of them are shown in Fig. 3:

- Point A indicates a missing connection between the AHU unit (green element) modelled in the Ventilation file and the wastewater pipes in the Piping model (blue pipe).
- Point B represents a missing link between a cold water supply route (blue pipe) from the Piping model and the boiler device (pink element) modelled in the Heating and cooling model.
- Point C shows a missing connection between a wastewater route (blue pipe) from the Piping model and the boiler device (pink element) modelled in the Heating & Cooling model.

3.1.2. IFC converter

The methodology utilises the IFC-LBD converter to effectively demonstrate the framework's application, as referenced in [46]. The primary motivation for choosing this tool was its ability to simplify the representation of relationships among MEP components. This simplification is achieved more efficiently compared to the approaches suggested by ifcOWL in the IFCtoRDF and IFCtoLBD tools [44,45].

A notable feature of the IFC-LBD converter is its customisable nature. It allows users to selectively determine which ontologies are included in the output file. It offers selection between BOT, FSO and TSO ontologies and semantic expression of IFC properties and product reference. This flexibility also extends to the choice of output file formats, with options between NQuads and JSON-LD formats. The tool is also developed as a Node Package Manager (NPM) library, written in TypeScript language, allowing for its usage by frontend or backend applications.

Moreover, the tool uses the IFC GUID as a reference while defining new elements and adding them to a database, enabling a bidirectional link between semantic representation and the original IFC file. The example result of the conversion of an IFC file is the graph representation presented in Fig. 4. The figure presents the valve element (1), connected to two transition elements (2.1 and 2.2) and associated with the "DomesticColdWater2" system (3). Additionally, the valve is placed in room A105 (4), is classified as 'fso:FlowController' (5) and has two associated ports (6.1 and 6.2).

Fig. 2. Domain-specific IFC models.

Fig. 3. Missing interdomain relation between IFC models.

Fig. 4. Example of conversion result based on IFC-LBD tool.

The presented in Fig. 4 example demonstrates an additional difference between the original assumptions of Flow System Ontology, and the approach offered by the IFC-LBD tool [37]. It proposed an extension of the FSO by an additional class `fso:Port` to reflect the `IfcPort` elements. Following this trend, the converter uses a similar approach suggested by buildingSMART documentation [50]. Such bidirectional relation is

highlighted by blue arrows in Fig. 5. A predicate that connects two connected ports is defined as '`fso:connectedPort`' [51]. The proposed elements are linked with `IfcElements` by grey arrows in Fig. 5. The last element fully aligned with the original FSO's requirements is the directed link between these `IfcElements`, unambiguously defining which element supplies and receives a fluid.

Fig. 5. Semantic connection between MEP components according to FSO ontology, extended by IFC-LBD approach.

3.2. Methods

This section presents the Federating Cross-Domain BIM-Based Knowledge Graph, outlining a clear and systematic methodology for integrating diverse building models. A visual overview of the method is presented in Fig. 6 and demonstrates three main steps. Step 1 consists of converting individual IFC files and describing ontologies representing their content. The methodology then advances to uncovering new knowledge, focusing on identifying similarities within the spatial structures of selected models (step 2). This involves aligning elements such as IfcBuildingStorey and IfcSpace, detailed in sub-steps 2.1 and 2.2, which enrich the existing knowledge base with new connections, providing interdisciplinary links between similar entities. Finally, step 3 presents an approach to discovering new relationships among MEP components, guided by their geometrical characteristics and flow direction. The methodology offers a detailed roadmap for integrating BIM models, highlighting the critical steps in fostering a more interconnected and insightful building information ecosystem.

3.2.1. Step 1 – Conversion

The initial stage of workflow advocates employing an IFC-LBD converter for each domain-specific IFC file [46]. These IFC models are crafted utilising the Model View Definition (MVD) with the IFC 2x3 Coordination View 2.0 standard. Converter settings include BOT, FSO ontologies, IFC Properties and IFC product reference. Therefore, the outcome of this conversion is a TTL file. This resultant file encapsulates details about the model components, which, employing LBD ontologies, are then stored in a triple store.

3.2.2. Step 2 – Interdomain spatial structure similarities detection

After the successful conversion of the IFC files, the comparison is conducted on elements that delineate the spatial structure of the model. This entails comprehensively comparing all models, focusing on analysing spatial structural resemblances. These similarities are evaluated specifically within the framework of two IFC classes: IfcBuildingStorey and IfcSpace [52].

A new predicate is introduced to enhance clarity and precision in representing this relation within a physical entity. This addition differentiates from the 'owl:equivalentTo' predicate, which links equivalent

classes. The new predicate, 'ex:geometricallyEquivalent', is specifically utilised to connect two entities: bot:Space or bot:Storey. Its primary function is to explicitly indicate that elements modelled in different namespaces are, in fact, representations of the same element within a physical model. This distinction is critical for accurately classifying entities that are considered geometrically equivalent. The prefix "ex" is an abbreviation from the namespace "https://example.com", because any ontology formally containing such a predicate was not identified.

3.2.2.1. Step 2.1 – IfcBuildingStorey similarities. In the case of IfcBuildingStorey elements, the analysis of similarities focuses on two key properties: the name of the element (for example, 'Level 1') and its elevation, which marks the floor's vertical placement in relation to a reference point (such as '+6.45 m'). When these parameters match, it indicates that the compared entities are identical. Consequently, an additional predicate, 'ex:geometricallyEquivalent', is added to a database.

3.2.2.2. Step 2.2 – IfcSpace similarities. To identify similarities among IfcSpace elements, a more sophisticated method is required. Our framework moves beyond merely examining characteristic features by employing Constructive Solid Geometry (CSG) to analyze the similarities between two entities [52]. Specifically, this approach utilizes a CSG intersection operation, which produces a new geometric shape representing the shared volume of the two entities being compared. The process works as follows:

1. CSG Intersection Operation: This operation is performed on two IfcSpace elements to generate a shape representing the volume common to both elements.
2. Volume Comparison: The volume of the resulting intersected shape is then calculated.
3. Threshold Criteria: If the volume of this intersected shape constitutes 95 % or more of the total combined volume of the two original IfcSpace elements, it is determined that the two elements represent the same physical space within different domain-specific models.

When this criterion is met, the framework infers that the IfcSpace elements are geometrically equivalent. Consequently, a new predicate,

Fig. 6. Federating Cross-Domain BIM-Based Knowledge Graph – an overview of steps required for federating multiple domain-specific IFC models.

'ex:geometricallyEquivalent', is created and added to the triple store to link the two compared entities, thereby explicitly indicating their equivalence. This method ensures high accuracy in identifying corresponding spaces across different models, as it relies on a precise geometric analysis rather than superficial feature comparison.

3.2.3. Step 3 – Interdisciplinary MEP components connectivity analysis

The final step analyses MEP components' interconnectivity. This process is initiated by identifying unconnected IfcPort elements within diverse domain-specific models. This is feasible due to the IFC-LBD converter's feature, which maintains the bidirectional link between TTL representation and the IFC file. Detection of unconnected IfcPort elements is made using properties of IfcRelConnectsPorts relation [51]. Elements not used in these relations are detected and defined as unconnected entities.

After unconnected IfcPorts identification, the iteration process starts comparing elements between all models defined to be federated. The classification that two elements are interdomain connected is based on three conditions. The first condition is the Cartesian distance, denoted as d . Using assumptions from the analysis presented et al. [53], the methodology accepts that the distance between considered connectors should be 25 mm or less. This situation is presented in Fig. 7, where a pipe supplying water, modelled in a piping model, is analysed to be connected with a water heater modelled in a heating and cooling model. The next condition is the angle between the normal vector of ifcPorts, denoted as θ and presented in Fig. 7. The methodology assumes that the angle between them must be less or equal to one Cartesian degree [53]. Such a margin of tolerance is essential to accommodate potential modelling inaccuracies and to prevent the requirement for component overlap, which could otherwise result in potential modelling clashes when performing models' coordination. The limited distance and vector margin ensure that the close placement of contingent elements does not classify them as connected. Therefore, these two elements can be forwarded to the final condition, checking the interference of the flow direction.

According to the IFC schema documentation, each IfcPort entity is characterised by a property known as IfcFlowDirectionEnum [51]. This property is defined by four distinct categories [54]:

- SOURCE – The Port is a source of a flow (payload flows out of the connection).
- SINK – The port is a sink of a flow (payload flows into the connection).
- SOURCEANDSINK – Port is bidirectional (payload flows into the connection or out of the connection).
- NOTDEFINED – Port direction is unknown.

Based on the analysis by Teclaw et al. [53], a connection between

two IfcPort entities can be established only when the flow direction is unequivocally determined. Satisfying all conditions indicates that the two components are interconnected, which results in four new predicates added to a triple store. Two predicates link a pair of IfcElement entities by explicitly determining the flow direction between them, and two additional predicates follow the approach aligned with the conversion tool [46].

4. Demo application

The "LBD-Online-Merge" application is specifically designed to validate the methods discussed in Section 3.2 through practical usage of the IFC models introduced in Section 3.1.1. Developed using Node.js, TypeScript, and the React framework, the app allows for serverless operation akin to a standard website, negating the need to transmit or store user data externally. It is made publicly available on GitHub¹ and Zenodo [55].

The application follows the workflow presented in Fig. 6. Utilization of the application initiates with the selecting and uploading the IFC models to federate. The models are displayed with their names in the panel after successfully uploading, as shown in Fig. 8, presenting the application interface. Each model has the option to assign a unique namespace URI, aiding in the differentiation of data sources post-federation; for instance, the namespace URI for an architectural model might be customized as "https://www.sample.org/architecture/". This feature simplifies the identification of data origins following federation. The next option is a selection of parsers used for model description between BOT, FSO, Products, and Properties.

The next step is launched by clicking the "Load and merge" button, which initiates the conversion of IFC models to TTL format and the subsequent data storage in the triple store. The application then identifies relationships between spatial structure elements, comparing all levels (step 2.1) across models to detect "geometricallyEquivalent" elements, thereby enriching the triple store with new knowledge. A similar process is applied in comparing IfcSpaces (step 2.2). Then, the application automatically analyses unconnected ports between IFC models, following the assumptions presented in step 3.

After the federation process, the application enables users to execute SPARQL construct queries to test the data, presenting the results in an interactive graph format. Furthermore, the federated data can be downloaded as a TTL file, offering a valuable resource for subsequent database analysis or integration.

5. Results

The presented results follow the methodology proposed in Section 3.2, based on IFC models introduced in Section 3.1.1. All numbers, such as conversion time and number of triples or connections, come from

Fig. 7. Visualisation of interdomain connectivity analysis based on angle and distance calculation.

Fig. 8. Visual interface of LBD-Online-Merge demo application with four uploaded IFC files.

implementing the listed steps in the LBD-Online-Merge application.

5.1. Applying step 1 – Conversion

Upon applying the first step of the presented methodology, as detailed in section 3.1.1, to IFC models utilising the designated converter, we created a total of 61 581 triples. These triples comprehensively represent the placement and properties of IFC elements and the intricate relationships among these elements. Detailed statistics of the distribution of these triples across the various utilised ontologies are systematically presented in Table 2.

Table 3 complements the insights gained from Table 2 by providing a detailed breakdown of the conversion times for the IFC models. This data, critical for understanding the efficiency of the conversion process, showcases the time taken to convert each model into selected ontologies using the IFC-LBD tool, offering a comprehensive view of the time investment required for each model. Each number presented in Table 3 illustrates the conversion time model using ontology parsers. The number is an average of five conversions performed using the LBD-Online-Merge app. The application is hosted by the Google Chrome web browser using a computer with an Intel(R) Core(TM) i5-11400H processor with a base clock speed of 2.70 GHz, complemented by 32.0 GB of RAM and a GeForce GTX 1650 graphics card.

The quantity and nature of the resulting triples are influenced by

Table 2 Conversion process of the domain-specific BIM models using IFC-LBD converter.

Model name	Number of triples resulting from conversion parsers using the IFC-LBD tool [-]				Total [-]
	BOT	FSO	IFC Product	IFC Properties	
Architecture	570	0	588	4063	5221
Heating & Cooling	703	9344	755	5246	16,048
Piping	977	13,196	1109	7311	22,593
Ventilation	799	10,242	872	5806	17,719

Table 3 Conversion time of IFC models.

Model name	Conversion time to the selected parser, using the IFC-LBD tool [ms]				Total [ms]
	BOT	FSO	IFC Product	IFC Properties	
Architecture	34.63	2.43	29.78	366.21	433.04
Heating & Cooling	32.86	414.59	31.88	486.44	965.77
Piping	40.22	568.01	45.49	640.82	1294.54
Ventilation	34.10	452.95	49.96	397.85	934.87

factors such as the used schema’s complexity, the intricacies of the model, and the number of properties involved. The conversion metrics are consistent across the board, with the notable exception of the FSO representation within the architectural model. The ontology primarily emphasises elements with characteristics of MEP. Consequently, elements traditionally associated with architectural disciplines, such as walls, doors, and windows, are not represented using the FSO approach.

5.2. Applying step 2.1 – IfcBuildingStorey similarities

Through the application of Step 2.1 of the methodology, 36 ‘ex:geometricallyEquivalent’ predicates were added to the triple store, establishing connections among three distinct groups of IfcBuildingStorey elements (marked with green dashed rectangular frames around). These groups are identifiable as Level 0, Level 1, and the Roof level. The integration was facilitated by recognising similarities in naming conventions and elevation levels across these groups, as presented in Fig. 9. Notably, one red node placed in the figure’s bottom part is not connected to any other elements. This element represents a ‘Top of Foundations’ level located in the architectural model. This specific IfcBuildingStorey element does not find a corresponding component in other MEP models. All nodes representing IfcBuildingStorey presented in Fig. 9 contain the label, e.g. inst:M1x3 replacing the real GUID number, significantly

Fig. 9. IfcBuildingStorey duplications after applying methodology step 2.1.

reducing its readability. Moreover, all these nodes in the presented knowledge graph are classified as a ‘bot:Storey’ element, as marked by blue in Fig. 9.

5.3. Applying step 2.2 – IfcSpace similarities

Through the application of Step 2.2 of the methodology, 252 ‘ex:geometricallyEquivalent’ predicates were discovered, establishing connections among 21 distinct groups of elements. This effort was directed towards the spatial elements of these models, with the spaces being distributed as follows: ten spaces each were associated with Level 0 and Level 1, and one space was allocated to the Roof level. A deeper analysis of the number of links revealed that each space included in a model was connected to three other instances of the IfcSpace object. The number of new predicates confirms that each of the spaces included in a model has three predicates to other instances of an IfcSpace object located in other

domain-specific files, resulting in 63 new predicates per IFC model.

5.4. Applying step 3 – Interdisciplinary MEP components connectivity

In the final step of the methodology, a new connection was discovered between the MEP components of three IFC models. This step resulted in the creation of 24 new predicates. As shown in Listing 1, each connected pair of elements leads to adding four predicates, indicating six newly connected pairs of IfcElements. That number covers the expected interdomain connections number according to the assumptions made during the modelling process, as described in Section 3.1.1. Listing 1 presents the SPARQL query used to retrieve all predicates across models in two different namespaces. The data detailing the number of relationships between the models and their MEP components is outlined in Table 4.

The table indicates the creation of new triples exclusively among

```

1 PREFIX bot: <https://w3id.org/bot#>
2 PREFIX fso: <https://w3id.org/fso#>
3 PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>
4
5 SELECT ?namespace_1 ?namespace_2 ?predicate
6 WHERE {
7   ?element1 a bot:Element;
8   ?predicate ?element2 .
9   ?element2 a bot:Element.
10  BIND (REPLACE (str(?element1), "(.*)/(.*)", "$1") AS ?namespace_1)
11  BIND (REPLACE (str(?element2), "(.*)/(.*)", "$1") AS ?namespace_2)
12  FILTER (?namespace_1 != ?namespace_2)
13 }
    
```

Listing 1. Newly discovered connection between unconnected ifcPort and ifcElement instances.

Table 4

Number of newly created triples between domain-specific models after application step 3.

Model name	Number of triples resulting from applying step 3 of methodology			
	Architecture	Heating & Cooling	Piping	Ventilation
Architecture	0	0	0	0
Heating & Cooling	0	0	8	0
Piping	0	8	0	4
Ventilation	0	0	4	0

models containing MEP components. The absence of new triples between the Ventilation and Heating & Cooling models is attributed to the lack of common connection points, which aligns with the initial expectations. Conversely, the Architectural model did not present any IFCElements relevant for analysis in this methodology phase.

Using the LBD-Online-Merge application for four introduced IFC models, the implementation of steps 2.1, 2.2 and 3 was measured, resulting in the average federation time equal to 291.56 ms.

6. Discussion

6.1. Usage of federating Cross-Domain BIM-Based knowledge graph

The primary objective of developing the framework is to enhance flexibility and facilitate extracting information and relationships between models. In the instance showcased in Listing 2, the SPARQL query targets a specific element, designated as ?selectedAHU, and retrieves the terminal component associated with the sewage system. This scenario proposes the usage of the workflow in integrating and presenting information across multiple models.

A notable constraint in this approach is the lack of a standardised naming convention for systems within the IFC model. Systems are subject to arbitrary naming, which introduces potential areas for refinement. To overcome this, it would be advantageous for the framework to not solely depend on the system name, as shown in line 12 of Listing 2, but integrating classification standards and leveraging their codes could offer a more robust and reliable method for system identification and information retrieval within the framework. Using codification significantly improves the universality and intelligibility of queries, making them accessible across various languages. The outcomes of this approach, applied via a SPARQL query in Listing 2, are detailed in Table 5. The table features a single row with the system name responsible for transporting wastewater from the AHU. The second column highlights the terminal component of this system, which marks the end of the elements modelled within the model's scope. Beyond this terminal

Table 5

Results of SPARQL query from Listing 2 on federated graph database.

	systemName	lastElement
1	Sewage1	https://www.sample.org/piping/20hZ8vgD99AU_3FahFbav

component, the municipal sewage network commences an area not yet included in this framework but open for future extension and integration.

Furthermore, this query could be adapted to retrieve not only the final component but also trace all downstream flow segments from the "selectedAHU" to the "lastElement". By doing so, it would be possible to effectively visualize and highlight the entire flow path between these components within a BIM model viewer. This enhancement would provide a comprehensive view of the system's layout and interactions, thereby improving the usability and functionality of the model in practical scenarios.

Construction objects are complex structures requiring service works and replacing of compartments. Presented in Listing 3 example of a SPARQL query is used to identify shared values responsible for controlling the water supply flow to two water heater devices. When maintenance work or replacement is required for these devices, shutting down the water supply becomes necessary. This can be achieved through manual documentation review, visual inspection, or, more efficiently, by utilising a SPARQL query presented in Listing 3.

The application of the Listing 3 query identifies upstream elements (supplying fluid) classified as Flow Controllers. It results in returning two components. Despite the selection of devices placed in two IFC models, applying the proposed Federating Cross-Domain BIM-Based Knowledge Graphs allows a graph database to identify components sharing a valve but modelled in various domain-specific IFC files. The query from Listing 3 returns two components placed in the piping model with guids '3HbZfS9frEv8ijKqUDynQt' and '3HbZfS9frEv8ijKqUDynrk'. Such identification proves its value in broader contexts, like smart building management systems, where automated and precise control of building resources is crucial. Moreover, it enables smarter and more automated methods for detecting dependency between components instead of their manual identification through MEP schemas, 2D drawings or event BIM models, which provide the geometrical interpretation but not the knowledge linkage between interdomain models.

The final example, detailed in Listing 4, introduces a complex query that uses a selected space, identified by a URI, as its input. This space can be selected from a range of domain-specific models. In the first step, the query identifies all spaces linked through the 'ex:geometricallyEquivalent' predicate, establishing a correspondence with the chosen space across various models. Subsequently, the SPARQL query

```

1 PREFIX bot: <https://w3id.org/bot#>
2 PREFIX fso: <https://w3id.org/fso#>
3 PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>
4 PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
5 SELECT ?systemName ?lastElement
6 WHERE {
7   BIND (<http://www.sample.org/ventilation/0g8pVvDxXC8BAH10lVdXuo> as ?selectedAHU)
8   ?selectedAHU fso:suppliesFluidTo* ?lastElement.
9   ?system fso:hasComponent ?lastElement;
10      rdf:type fso:DistributionSystem;
11      rdfs:label ?systemName.
12   FILTER (CONTAINS (LCASE (?systemName), "sewage"))
13   FILTER NOT EXISTS {
14     ?lastElement fso:suppliesFluidTo ?beyondLastElement.
15   }
16 }

```

Listing 2. Getting last accessible component of sewage system connected to AHU.

```

1 PREFIX fso: <https://w3id.org/fso#>
2
3 SELECT DISTINCT ?valve
4 WHERE {
5     BIND (<http://www.sample.org/heatingandcooling/2_O2VU7ajFAP8YQh1myRCV> as ?DEVICE1)
6     BIND (<http://www.sample.org/piping/0DoXf6qmD2uA0W21bBqVAu> as ?DEVICE2)
7     ?DEVICE1 fso:hasFluidSuppliedBy* ?valve .
8     ?DEVICE2 fso:hasFluidSuppliedBy* ?valve .
9     ?valve a fso:FlowController .
10 }

```

Listing 3. Detection of shared valves for two selected devices.

```

1 PREFIX bot: <https://w3id.org/bot#>
2 PREFIX fso: <https://w3id.org/fso#>
3 PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>
4 PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
5 PREFIX owl: <http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#>
6 PREFIX ex: <http://example.com/ex#>
7
8 SELECT DISTINCT ?systemName ?spaceLabel ?valveLocationSpace
9 WHERE {
10     BIND (<http://www.sample.org/architecture/0BTBFw6f90Nfh9rP1dl_3S> as
?selectedSpace)
11     ?selectedSpace ex:geometricallyEquivalent ?otherDomainSpaceEquivalent
.
12
13     {
14         BIND (?selectedSpace AS ?combinedSpace)
15         ?combinedSpace bot:containsElement ?terminalElement .
16     }
17     UNION
18     {
19         BIND (?otherDomainSpaceEquivalent AS ?combinedSpace)
20         ?combinedSpace bot:containsElement ?terminalElement .
21     }
22     ?terminalElement a fso:Terminal .
23     ?terminalElement fso:hasFluidSuppliedBy ?elementAfterTerminal .
24     ?system a fso:hasComponent ?elementAfterTerminal ;
25     a fso:DistributionSystem ;
26     rdfs:label ?systemName ;
27     fso:hasComponent ?component .
28     ?component a fso:FlowController .
29     ?valveLocationSpace a bot:Space ;
30     bot:containsElement ?component ;
31     rdfs:label ?spaceLabel .

```

Listing 4. SPARQL query detecting all valves controlling supply of fluids to selected space.

identifies terminal components that interact with the selected space, primarily in terms of fluid supply. The query continues to trace upstream components, eventually pinpointing all elements integral to flow control within the system. As a final step, the query retrieves the if-FlowController elements. It returns the name of a system interacting with a selected space, the label of the room in which the corresponding flow controller (for example, valve) is located and its URL. The result of

the Listing 4 SPARQL query is presented in Table 6.

The selected space is labelled B103 and named ‘Kitchen’. It requires two piping systems for cold and hot water supply. Additionally, it has a ‘HydronicSupply2’ system for fluid delivery to the room’s radiator, linked with the heating and cooling model. In the demo model, all valves are in space ‘B105’, easily found without advanced technologies like BIM and knowledge graphs. However, this task can be challenging and time-consuming in larger commercial buildings with many floors. Therefore, using the methodology outlined in this paper could greatly optimize the process of identifying dependencies between rooms, devices, and control elements.

6.2. Benefits

Constructing a Federated Knowledge Graph from domain-specific BIM models involves transforming individual files and integrating them. This process includes converting models to RDF-compatible TTL

Table 6

Results of running SPARQL query from Listing 4.

	systemName	spaceLabel	valveLocationSpace
1	Domestic Cold Water 1	B105	http://www.sample.org/piping/3S Gml5%24R50rxo38aZpfmvm
2	HydronicSupply2	B105	http://www.sample.org/heatingandcooling/0_4sOlpXT7gftkTUEd3uDA
3	Domestic Hot Water 1	B105	http://www.sample.org/piping/3S Gml5%24R50rxo38aZpfmvm

format, which takes 3628 ms (step 1), and federating these models, which takes an additional 291 ms (steps 2–3). Consequently, federation accounts for 8.02 % of the total conversion time. This ratio aligns with RQ1, demonstrating an efficient method for creating a federated knowledge graph. Unlike manual methods, this process is both rapid and efficient. Clear rules have been established to validate connections between components, ensuring a deterministic approach that sets unambiguous boundaries. This is crucial for modellers aiming to guarantee the consistency of inter-domain model connections, which is achieved without relying on manual adjustments whenever a model is updated.

The framework's modular nature suggests its potential encapsulation as a microservice, promoting seamless integration with CDE platforms. Data uploaded to the SHARED container could be effectively merged after BIM model verification and reaching a certain status code, enhancing user collaboration and facilitating the integration with validating algorithms. Such integration and conversion triggering could be done using webhooks, notifying the service about the need to process a file's revision and updating a federated graph database.

Integrating domain-specific models into a Federated Knowledge Graph is fundamental to addressing RQ2. This process involves a series of structured steps designed to ensure that each model contributes effectively to the comprehensive knowledge architecture. This integration enables the combination of diverse data sources and enhances the graph's ability to represent complex relationships and interactions within the built environment accurately. By carefully aligning and connecting spatial and structural elements across different models, the framework establishes a robust basis for achieving a comprehensive and coherent integration, highlighting the practical and theoretical value of the research.

The framework employs a sequential approach to ensure the integration process's scalability. Initially, models are converted into graphs, and the retrieved data sets the stage for the rest of the integration process, which is systematically divided into two main parts. The first part focuses on integrating spatial structure elements and defining previously undefined relationships, primarily using the `IfcBuildingStorey` class. Although connections between three storeys in four different IFC models were successfully established, one `IfcBuildingStorey` failed to link due to the absence of corresponding elements. The method implemented in step 2.1 is straightforward and easily verifiable; however, it relies on precise elevation and naming parameters. This strict adherence to naming conventions means that any minor error or deviation could disrupt the linkage between components. Additionally, in real-world applications, such as in structural engineering, floor levels are often lowered by the thickness of finish layers for modelling convenience, which presents an opportunity to refine this aspect and make this point of the framework more robust.

The second part of the spatial structure analysis involves the `IfcSpace` class, which is more complex than the `IfcBuildingStorey`. The comparison mechanism used in step 2.2 applies a 95 % overlapping ratio to effectively identify elements that mirror spaces in other domain models. This approach is advantageous because it allows for small deviations between elements, with the flexibility to adjust the ratio based on factors such as building type, design stage, or the defined Level of Information Need. Introducing the 'ex:geometricallyEquivalent' predicate is critical as it clarifies that while two elements may differ in the modelling context, they represent the same physical entity. This predicate also applies to point clouds or boundary representations (BREP), expanding its use across various AEC applications and life cycle stages.

The second part of the proposed methodology is the identification of missing connections between MEP components. This analysis successfully identified all six intended connection points between MEP models, aligning with the initial expectations. The rule-based approach ensures that the detection of new connections is clear and replicable. However, the method faces challenges with incomplete information from IFC models. Enhancements could include adding detailed parameters describing the port's shape and size and ensuring connectivity based on

geometric similarities. Specifying the `IfcPort` type would clarify system compatibility, which is straightforward for single-system components but challenging for multi-system components with multiple `IfcPort` entities.

The framework's sequential nature not only supports targeted extensions for specific components or domain specifications but also highlights its potential to adapt to various architectural, engineering, and construction scenarios. This adaptability increases its applicability across different project requirements and complexities, ensuring it can meet a wide range of industry needs.

Implementing a BIM-based Federated Knowledge Graph significantly enhances interoperability and optimizes data transfer throughout the building lifecycle, from design to operation. This framework offers substantial benefits for various stakeholders, primarily by enabling contextual queries and fostering a deeper understanding of the interdependencies among interdisciplinary data. This facilitates a more effective utilization of information, serving as a structured and reliable input for the Digital Twin concept during an asset's operational phase.

An additional advantage of this approach, particularly relevant to RQ3, is its straightforward and low-effort implementation for real design teams. The methodology requires adherence to a clearly defined set of rules for spatial structure components, including following a consistent naming convention and duplicating architectural spaces across domain-specific BIM models. For MEP connectivity, a tolerance of 2.5 cm ensures that ports must be deliberately placed in close proximity, enhancing accuracy and reducing the risk of model clashes.

Moreover, integrating spaces or floors simplifies the querying of integrated quantities and material take-offs, directly addressing RQ3 and improving project management efficiency. This streamlined integration not only supports the operational phase but also enhances the overall lifecycle management of building projects, ensuring that all stakeholders can access and interact with the most relevant and up-to-date information and their context.

Section 6.1 outlines use cases illustrating the potential applications of the concept. While employing SPARQL queries for a common valve shutting down flow to two mechanical equipment might seem trivial for smaller structures, its relevance escalates for facility managers and maintenance personnel overseeing larger, complex structures like skyscrapers with multiple systems, dozens of floors, and thousands of valves across numerous technical rooms. In such settings, this concept significantly eases the identification of inter-system connections and control elements for specific zones or floors, thereby enhancing operational efficiency and maintenance procedures.

7. Conclusion

This study has addressed critical interoperability challenges in the construction industry by introducing a novel methodology for federating cross-domain BIM-based knowledge graphs. By linking diverse architectural and MEP models through the "LBD-Online-Merge" demo application, this approach has demonstrated how semantic web technologies can significantly enhance data management and construction workflows, leading to more efficient and optimized building operations.

The proposed methodology and its modularization ensure the framework can be efficiently integrated with Common Data Environment (CDE) platforms. It serves as critical data preparation for the operational phase of a building's lifecycle or as input for a Digital Twin. The paper outlines a set of clear guidelines for data integration and model federation, facilitating robust and repeatable processes. This approach establishes a foundational strategy for constructing semantically rich digital twins of the built environment, enhancing the management of building systems from design through to operation. Semantic web technologies are crucial in enhancing BIM capabilities, contributing to smarter building management, reduced operational costs, and greater sustainability in the construction industry. This holistic approach supports advanced data-driven management practices, paving the way for a

future where building operations are significantly more integrated and intelligent.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

In developing this manuscript, ChatGPT, a generative AI language model, was utilised to improve the readability and grammar syntax.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Wojciech Teclaw: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Conceptualization. **James O'Donnel:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Ville Kukkonen:** Writing – original draft, Software. **Pieter Pauwels:** Writing – review & editing. **Nathalie Labonnote:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Eilif Hjelseth:** Supervision, Project administration.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The data is published to a GitHub repository and Zenodo, as referenced in the paper.

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